

Data-drivenness, novelty, and interdisciplinarity in the study of criminology

Anne Kavalerschik¹

¹*akavaler@iu.edu*

Department of Informatics; Department of Sociology, Indiana University,
Bloomington, Indiana (USA)

Abstract

With the discipline of criminology as a case study, we explore how papers using what can broadly be considered “data-driven methods” leverage novelty to experience citation benefits. The study of criminal justice is notable because it is a discipline in which applied and also controversial methods such as predictive policing and automated bail allotment have emerged in recent years (Brayne and Christin 2020; Brayne 2020). Many of these technologies rely on the combination of traditional criminal justice concepts with novel computational methods. We generate different measures of novelty, including the scientific journal and article content of references, to demonstrate that articles that use data-driven methods, such as machine learning, experience a particular advantage in impact measured by citation. We create estimations of article content using Top2Vec and compare novelty as measured by atypical combinations of references (Uzzi et al. 2013) and novelty as measured through sub-field integration (Moody 1996). To conclude, we discuss the larger implications that research in the era of “Big Data” has on the production of scientific knowledge and technology.

Introduction

The increasing ubiquity of data-driven methods in the criminal justice system has drawn widespread attention from scholars, activists, and policymakers (Lavorgna and Ugwudike 2021). In particular, these groups have raised a number of concerns about the assumptions underlying the algorithmic technologies that increasingly play a decisionmaking or predictive role (Benjamin 2019). While scholars of science and technology have long studied how interdisciplinarity and novelty generate new scientific insights and disrupt existing paradigms (Schilling and Green 2011; Uzzi et al. 2013; Leahey and Moody 2014; Funk and Owen-Smith 2017), less is understood about how specifically data-driven methods are integrated into existing scholarly paradigms. The increasing popularity of computational methods into a wide range of decision-making processes suggests that data-drivenness is a growing trend in many scholarly fields that may not traditionally use such methods (Hu and Zhang 2018).

Interdisciplinarity is known to be a high-risk, high-reward endeavor (Leahey, Beckman, and Stanko 2017; Foster, Rzhetsky, and Evans 2015). Perhaps data-driven methods, however, occupy a particular position that leverages the benefits of scientific novelty while avoiding the pitfalls. Given that data-driven methods can be broadly applied to a wide diversity of research areas, it is important to identify the precise impact of increasing data-drivenness in fields that may not traditionally use those methods (Brady 2019).

The field of criminology is one such field in which data-driven methods are increasingly integrated (Halterlein 2021; Lavorgna and Ugwudike 2021). Additionally, criminology is also a field in which there are increasing amounts of applied, data-driven technologies such as predictive policing (Brayne 2020) and automated bail allotment (Christin 2020); technologies that leverage machine learning methods to automate decision-making processes traditionally performed by expert practitioners in the field. Therefore, in criminology, we can observe the increasing integration of data-drivenness into technology. To understand whether this is occurring in science, we explore changes in the knowledge base of criminological research

from 1992-2017, and use co-citation patterns to identify how criminological research draws on novel, computational methods.

Data and methods

Data were collected through the Web of Science (WoS). We downloaded articles categorized under the WoS’s “Criminology and Penology” Research Area from 1992-2017. The period was chosen because 1992 is the earliest year for which there are abstracts. There were 35,132 articles in the initial set, of which 24,291 remained after dropping articles that had no references listed.

Using the references we study the knowledge base of criminological publications over time using the journals, categories, and topical content of articles. Uzzi et al. (2013) used journals to identify atypical combinations. In addition to journals, we also use journal classifications from (Milojevic 2020) and topical content classified through Top2Vec (Angelov 2020). This embedding approach is used to discover topics in large collections of documents, and thereby give insight to the main themes in this corpus. 281 topics are generated out of ‘top2vec’, which we hierarchically reduce to 100.

Out of these 100 topics, we identified 5 that, based on their top keywords can be considered as implying quantitative, statistical, mathematical, and/or computational approaches, which we interpret to constitute the category of data-drivenness. In Table 1, we show these topics and their associated keywords. Topic modeling is based on the assumption that documents can have multiple topics, and we identify “data-driven” articles by articles whose highest topical prevalence is one of these topics. There were 1,702 of these articles.

Table 1: “Data-driven” topics

topic number	topic keywords
9	convergent, validity, psychometric, scales, retest
11	static, auc, predictive, recidivism, yls
25	spatial, locations, burglary, burglaries, spatially
40	meta, randomized, designs, sizes, rigorous
85	spots, hot, patrol, spot, foot

Using the attributes of journals, journal classifications, and topic categories, we generate estimates of novelty based on the protocol by Uzzi et al. (2013). Uzzi et al. (2013) found that scientific articles that use atypical combinations in their references have a higher scientific impact than their counterparts. To perform a similar analysis, we use a citation-switching algorithm from Bradley et al. (2020), which works comparably well to the Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithm used by Uzzi et al. (2013) et al. but with more computational efficiency. Using these permutations, we then calculate the novelty of an article’s references based on those references’ (journal, journal classification, and topic) attributes. We do this by comparing the observed frequency of co-citation attributes with the frequency i distribution of pairs generated by citation switching and generating a z score for each pair. Z -scores above 0 imply more conventional pairings, while z scores below zero indicate more novel pairings (Uzzi et al. 2013; Bradley et al. 2020).

Results

First, we explore the knowledge base of criminological publications based on categories created by Milojevic (2020). In Figure 1, we show the prevalence of journal classifications over time, as well the Gini coefficient over time. Predictably, the bulk of criminological articles draw on references which belong to the broad category of “Social sciences”, followed by “Psychology” and “Medical sciences”. Based just on the Gini coefficient decreasing over time, the distribution of those references’ broad categories becomes more equal, although there is a significant jump from 2015 to 2017.

Figure 1: Distribution of journal classifications based on Milojevic (2020) in references of criminological articles 1992-2017

In 2, we show that the relationship between atypical references used over time in criminological publications is complicated. For articles across the entire corpus, there does not appear to be a relationship between year and median z-score, but there does appear to be a negative relationship between an article’s 10th percentile z-score and citation score. As the 10th percentile z-score is an indicator of a paper’s more unusual combination, this implies that, over time, criminological publications’ more unusual combinations get progressively *more* unusual. This is also the case for articles in the top 50% by citation, but the relationship is different for articles in the top 10% by citation. For these articles, which represent the papers with the highest scientific impact in the corpus, there is a positive relationship with median z-score and time, and no relationship between 10th percentile z-score and time.

Figure 2: Atypical combinations over time

Whether the knowledge base of criminological publications is trending more atypical over time is unclear. It appears that “hit” papers, or papers which have the top 10% of citations over the entire corpus, have a higher median z-score over time, but papers in the top 50% of citations and papers throughout the entire corpus show a decrease in the 10th percentile z-score over time. As demonstrated by previous research, interdisciplinary research that brings together otherwise disparate fields does not have a straightforward payoff in terms of citation (Leahey, Beckman, and Stanko 2017).

Figure 3: Median and 10th percentile z-score for data-driven vs. non-data-driven abstracts

In figure 3, we show that data-driven articles have atypical combinations in their references at a higher level than their non-data-driven counterparts. This is particularly true for articles’ 10th percentile z-score, implying that data-driven articles may constitute a large portion of articles which have particularly atypical pairings of references. To analyze whether this is associated with scientific impact, we model the relationship between 10th percentile z-score, year of publication, and being prevalent in a data-driven topic.

In table 2, we show the output of the following linear regression: *cite count*
 $= \alpha + \beta_1 \text{year} + \beta_2 \text{zpt10} + \beta_3 \text{data topic}$

These results imply that there is a negative relationship between-year published (with 1992 being the lower bound and 2017 the upper bound), demonstrating that papers published earlier have more time to accrue citations. Additionally, these results show that there is a negative association with the 10th percentile z-score and citation impact, and a positive relationship with being a data-driven article and citation, all of which are significant at the .05 level.

Table 2: Linear regression of year, atypicality, and data-drivenness

	coef	std err	t	P > t 	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	3509.3739	62.867	55.822	0.000	3386.151	3632.597
year	-1.7391	0.031	-55.567	0.000	-1.800	-1.678
zpt10	-0.0316	0.002	-14.657	0.000	-0.036	-0.027
data topic	6.1989	0.750	8.268	0.000	4.729	7.669

Discussion

By using a combination of topic modeling and citation analysis, we have investigated criminological research publications from 1992-2017, as well as the associations of novelty, data-drivenness, and scientific impact within these publications. Analyzing the atypicality of citation patterns offers further insight into its evolving knowledge base and its relationship to scientific impact (Uzzi et al. 2013). We find that while there is no straightforward trend in regards to the use of atypical combinations over time, there is an association between atypical combinations and topics related to data-drivenness, and that both of these are associated with citation benefits. However, identifying the causal relationship between atypicality, data-drivenness, and scientific impact is outside the scope of this research.

Future directions will continue to investigate interdisciplinarity in the case of applied, data-driven methods. This work demonstrates several possibilities for applying scientometric methods to answer field-specific questions about how interdisciplinarity manifests in particular domains. Given the accelerating integration of data-driven methods into applications in criminal justice and beyond, there are a number of open questions about the effect of applying computational or quantitative methods to traditional fields in novel ways. Whether and how other scholarly fields' knowledge bases will evolve given the rising sophistication of computational methods and technologies will continue to be an important question.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported in part by Lilly Endowment, Inc., through its support for the Indiana University Pervasive Technology Institute.

References

Angelov, Dimo. 2020. *Top2Vec: Distributed Representations of Topics*, arXiv:2008.09470, August. Accessed November 29, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv>.

- 2008.09470. arXiv: arXiv:2008.09470.
- Benjamin, Ruha. 2019. *Race after Technology: Abolitionist Tools for the New Jim Code*. Cambridge, UK ; Medford, MA: Polity. isbn: 978-1-50952640-6 978-1-5095-2639-0.
- Bradley, James, Sitaram Devarakonda, Avon Davey, Dmitriy Korobskiy, Siyu Liu, Djamil Lakhdar-Hamina, Tandy Warnow, and George Chacko. 2020. "Co-Citations in Context: Disciplinary Heterogeneity Is Relevant." *Quantitative Science Studies* 1, no. 1 (February): 264–276. issn: 2641-3337. <https://doi.org/10.1162/qss.a.00007>.
- Brady, Henry E. 2019. "The Challenge of Big Data and Data Science." *Annual Review of Political Science* 22, no. 1 (May): 297–323. issn: 1094-2939, 1545-1577. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-090216-023229>.
- Brayne, Sarah. 2020. *Predict and Surveil: Data, Discretion, and the Future of Policing*. Oxford University Press, October. isbn: 978-0-19-068409-9.
- Brayne, Sarah, and Ang`ele Christin. 2020. "Technologies of Crime Prediction: The Reception of Algorithms in Policing and Criminal Courts." *Social Problems*, no. spaa004 (March). issn: 0037-7791. <https://doi.org/10.1093/socpro/spaa004>.
- Christin, Ang`ele. 2020. "The Ethnographer and the Algorithm: Beyond the Black Box." *Theory and Society* (August). issn: 1573-7853. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11186-020-09411-3>.
- Foster, Jacob G., Andrey Rzhetsky, and James A. Evans. 2015. "Tradition and Innovation in Scientists' Research Strategies." *American Sociological Review* 80, no. 5 (October): 875–908. issn: 0003-1224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122415601618>.
- Funk, Russell J., and Jason Owen-Smith. 2017. "A Dynamic Network Measure of Technological Change." *Management Science* 63, no. 3 (March): 791–817. issn: 0025-1909, 1526-5501. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2015.2366>.
- Ha`lterlein, Jens. 2021. "Epistemologies of Predictive Policing: Mathematical Social Science, Social Physics and Machine Learning." *Big Data & Society* 8, no. 1 (January): 20539517211003118. issn: 2053-9517. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211003118>.
- Hu, Jiming, and Yin Zhang. 2018. "Measuring the Interdisciplinarity of Big Data Research: A Longitudinal Study." *Online Information Review* 42, no. 5 (January): 681–696. issn: 14684527. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-12-2016-0361>.
- Lavorgna, Anita, and Pamela Ugwudike. 2021. "The Datafication Revolution in Criminal Justice: An Empirical Exploration of Frames Portraying Data-Driven Technologies for Crime Prevention and Control." *Big Data & Society* 8, no. 2 (July): 20539517211049670. issn: 2053-9517. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211049670>.
- Leahey, Erin, Christine M. Beckman, and Taryn L. Stanko. 2017. "Prominent but Less Productive: The Impact of Interdisciplinarity on Scientists' Research." *Administrative Science Quarterly* 62, no. 1 (March): 105–139. issn: 0001-8392, 1930-3815. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0001839216665364>.
- Leahey, Erin, and James Moody. 2014. "Sociological Innovation through Subfield Integration." *Social Currents* 1, no. 3 (October): 228–256. issn: 2329-4965. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2329496514540131>.
- Milojevic, Stasa. "Practical Method to Reclassify Web of Science Articles into Unique Subject Categories and Broad Disciplines." *Quantitative Science Studies* 1, no. 1 (February): 183–206. issn: 2641-3337. <https://doi.org/10.1162/qss.a.00014>.
- Moody, R. Adam. 1996. "Report: Reexamining Brain Drain from the Former Soviet Union." *The Nonproliferation Review* 3, no. 3 (September): 92–97. issn: 1073-6700, 1746-1766. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10736709608436643>.
- Schilling, Melissa A., and Elad Green. 2011. "Recombinant Search and Breakthrough Idea Generation: An Analysis of High Impact Papers in the Social Sciences." *Research Policy* 40, no. 10 (December): 1321–1331. issn: 0048-7333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2011.06.009>.

Uzzi, Brian, Satyam Mukherjee, Michael Stringer, and Ben Jones. 2013. "Atypical Combinations and Scientific Impact." *Science* 342, no. 6157 (October): 468–472. issn: 0036-8075, 10959203. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1240474>.